

ParlaSent: Mapping Sentiment in Political Discourse with Large Language Models

Michal Mochtak¹, Peter Rupnik², Taja Kuzman³, and Nikola Ljubešić⁴

(Preprint)

¹ Department of Political Science, Radboud University, Heyendaalseweg 141, 6525 AJ Nijmegen, Netherlands; ORCID: 0000-0001-5598-5642; E-mail: michal.mochtak@ru.nl.

² Department of Knowledge Technologies, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia; ORCID: 0009-0000-9700-3686; E-mail: peter.rupnik@ijs.si.

³ Department of Knowledge Technologies, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia; ORCID: 0000-0001-7436-9896; E-mail: taja.kuzman@ijs.si.

⁴ Department of Knowledge Technologies, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia; ORCID: 0000-0001-7169-9152; E-mail: nikola.ljubestic@ijs.si.

Abstract

This paper introduces ParlaSent, a deep learning model for multilingual sentiment analysis, specifically designed to study sentiment in political discourse. Built upon the XLM-R-parla model—a domain-specific multilingual transformer based on XLM-RoBERTa—ParlaSent benefits from additional pre-training on 1.72 billion words from the parliamentary proceedings of 26 European parliaments. ParlaSent outperforms sentiment dictionaries and achieves performance comparable to GPT-4o in a zero-shot sentiment classification setting, while being significantly faster and more cost-effective. By enabling high-quality sentiment analysis across multiple languages, ParlaSent enhances the study of political sentiment within European democracies and supports efficient, large-scale sentiment annotation in parliamentary discourse.

Keywords

sentiment; sentiment analysis; language model; Europe

Disclosure Statement

The authors declare that they have no relevant financial or non-financial competing interests to disclose.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the project "Large Language Models for Digital Humanities" (GC-0002), and the research programme "Language resources and technologies for Slovene" (P6-0411), both funded by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS). The authors also acknowledge the OSCARS project, which has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

Word count

5882 (without references)

Introduction

Parliamentary proceedings are a cornerstone of political systems, offering insight into elite political dynamics and serving as a lens into politicians' preferences, positions, and rhetorical strategies (Proksch and Slapin 2015; Lakoff 2004). Understanding these deliberations is essential for analyzing political evolution and consequences, particularly through the emotional tone and sentiment conveyed in discourse (Chilton 2004; Powell 2004). Emotions play a crucial role in political communication, influencing affective polarization and democratic stability (Young and Soroka 2012; Garrett et al. 2014; Mason 2015). The rise of online media has amplified the importance of sentiment analysis, yet empirical applications beyond English remain limited, often relying on outdated methods that introduce inference noise (González-Bailón and Paltoglou 2015; Duval and Pétry 2016; Proksch et al. 2019). However, advances in computational linguistics and AI now enable more systematic, multilingual sentiment analysis across diverse political contexts.

This paper introduces a multilingual sentiment classification model called *ParlaSent*. This model is presented as a tool that anyone can use free of charge without needing a deep knowledge of large language models and their architecture. The aim is to lower the barriers to employing this and similar models in political science research and to foster greater interest in natural language processing tools within the political science domain. We demonstrate the model's utility and robustness on corpora of parliamentary debates from 26 national parliaments in Europe. As a collaborative work of computer and political scientists, the technical aspects of the model and its validation were presented in Mochtak et al. (2024). This paper takes the technical baseline of the original paper and develops it into a practical demonstration of the model's capabilities in the political science domain. We do this by providing a step-by-step overview of how the model works from a technical perspective and then demonstrate its utility and validity in two case studies commonly seen in political science research. We argue that the sentiment classification model allows for answering a wide range of research questions concerning political framing, attitudes, and sentiment in European parliaments and beyond. To make the model even more approachable to a wide range of political scientists, we accompany the paper with a tutorial in an executable Jupyter Notebook providing simple walk-through guidance on how to use the sentiment model for annotating custom data using Google Colab.

Studying sentiment in political discourse

In recent years, the proliferation of computational methods has opened up new avenues for sentiment analysis with relatively high accuracy rates (Das and Singh 2023; Tan, Lee, and Lim 2023). However, within mainstream political science, this progress has been slow to fully materialize. Abercrombie and Batista-Navarro (2020) discovered that the majority of automated applications in the field, particularly those focused on parliamentary debates and political stances, remain on the periphery rather than at the core of political science research. Addressing this disparity is crucial, given the recognition in empirical political science research that individuals often engage with politics through emotions (Masch and Gabriel 2020).

Recent studies have highlighted how political leaders leverage violent and populist rhetoric to emotionally connect with citizens (Gerstlé and Nai 2019; Piazza 2020; Masch and Gabriel 2020). Especially negative framing has proven to be very effective in influencing public sentiment (Widmann 2021) leading to detrimental outcomes such as affective polarization, negative partisanship, and political sectarianism (Druckman et al. 2021; Iyengar, Sood, and Lelkes 2012; Abramowitz and Webster 2016; Mason 2018; Finkel et al. 2020). The long-term ramifications of these emotional manipulations on the electorate can be disastrous. Understanding these processes goes hand in hand with the strategies for maintaining resilient democratic societies and preventing further polarization.

In the realm of practical applications within the political science domain, sentiment analysis is predominantly utilized in approaches focused on machine learning on the one hand (Abercrombie and Batista-Navarro 2018; Bansal, Cardie, and Lee 2008), and dictionary-based sentiment extraction on the other (Honkela et al. 2014; Proksch et al. 2019). The paper is embedded in the latest wave of articles focused on modeling sentiment utilizing transformer models and transfer learning (Widmann and Wich 2023; Laurer et al. 2024). The approach leverages pre-trained large language models trained on vast amounts of text data to initialize the parameters of a new model, which is then fine-tuned on a specific task or dataset of interest (e.g., detection of sentiment, hate speech, or topics). This approach allows the new model to benefit from the general linguistic and world knowledge learned during pre-training, enhancing its performance on

downstream tasks with much less manually labeled data. By adapting the pre-trained model to the nuances of the target task through fine-tuning, transfer learning enables efficient and effective utilization of learned representations for various natural language processing tasks, including sentiment analysis (Kroon et al. 2023).

ParlaSent 101

ParlaSent is a transformer-based deep learning model trained for the task of sentiment analysis of textual data. The model is a result of an annotation campaign focused on experimenting with training a multilingual sentiment classifier in parliamentary proceedings of low-resourced European languages. The initiative aimed to address the existing lack of similar resources that would go beyond the usual suspects, such as English, German, or French. The effort resulted in the annotation of 18 200 sentences sampled from seven European parliaments – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Czech Republic, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, and the United Kingdom. The sentences were annotated with a six-level coding schema (negative [0] – mixed negative [1] – neutral negative [2] – neutral positive [3] – mixed positive [4] – positive [5]), which was then used for training a classification model predicting a sentiment score on the scale from 0-5 ([0] fully negative – [5] fully positive).

The data annotation was organized in multiple iterations, with two highly trained annotators per dataset. Annotators underwent around ten hours of training before annotating up to 75 sentences per hour, amounting to 35 hours per annotator per dataset. For the BCS and English test sets, only one annotator was used, but quality control measures were still applied. Despite efforts to minimize disagreements, the inter-annotator agreement (IAA) using Krippendorff's alpha was only satisfactory ($\alpha \approx 0.52$ for six sentiment classes; $\alpha \approx 0.61$ for three sentiment classes), indicating the subjective nature of sentiment perception. Disagreements were resolved through reconciliation, with additional external review for complicated cases. For further details concerning the annotation process, see Mochtak et al. (2024).

The motivation to annotate a limited amount of data in just a few languages and then generalize the learned knowledge over languages not included in the fine-tuning process is possible due to recent advancements in

the fields of natural language processing, driven namely by the transformer language models (colloquially referred to as *transformers*). Transformers exploit a neural sequential modeling technique called self-attention, which, in simple terms, allows for modeling the dependency of the various elements in a sequence of words in natural language (Vaswani et al. 2017). For instance, how the valence shifter *not* in the sentence “I will not be supporting this bill, and therefore it is destined to fail” changes the meaning of the surrounding words. This is possible thanks to the self-attention mechanism, which allows “paying” attention to the relations of a given word with all other words in the analyzed sequence of text. When combined with self-supervision strategies, which rely on simple techniques to transform raw text into a series of prediction tasks, the model can learn to understand the nuanced relationships between words and phrases.

One of the most common examples using self-supervision is a prediction of a masked word in a sequence of words, typically a sentence (e.g., identifying the word missing in “I will [MASK] be supporting this bill ...”). Through this process, the model learns about word interactions within a context. For instance, given the local context, two words, “not” and “surely,” might both seem plausible. However, when considering the whole context (“... and therefore the bill is destined to fail.”), the word “not” becomes the more likely candidate for the masked word. Through this self-supervision mechanism, the model, in its pre-training phase, teaches itself to guess accurately what word is most probably masked in a sequence of words. As a result, the model learns how to numerically represent the meaning of words in their context defined by semantically meaningful units, such as sentences, paragraphs, or whole documents. When the numeric representations of these text units are associated with specific categories (i.e., labels), the model can be further fine-tuned to learn the relationship between word representations and the assigned labels, enabling it to apply this newly acquired skill to distinguish learned patterns in previously unseen data (Merritt 2022).

Multilingual transformer models can be considered an empirical step further. The models are pre-trained on large quantities of raw text in different languages, which not only allows for modeling dependence of words in various languages but also facilitates the internal representations of words and sentences across languages to be comparable. In this context, the language models can be considered data compression machines. As languages are not isolated systems, it is possible to represent identical and similar meanings of words and

their interactions in different languages in the same way. This is why it is possible to train a multilingual transformer model on the task of sentiment identification for one language and successfully apply the model to a language unseen during fine-tuning, but seen during the self-supervision pre-training phase.

Our training process utilized the principles of transfer learning of a multilingual LLM specifically developed for the purpose of modeling political language. We trained the first-of-its-kind domain-specific multilingual transformer language model for political science applications called XLM-R-parla¹. It is based on XLM-RoBERTa-large vanilla model (Y. Liu et al. 2019), which we additionally pre-trained on 1.72 billion words from parliamentary proceedings of 26 parliaments included in the ParlaMint database v3.0 (Erjavec, Ogrodniczuk, et al. 2023) and the EuroParl database of proceedings from the European Parliament (Koehn 2005). We selected the XLM-RoBERTa model due to its multilingual nature, as it was pre-trained on 100 languages. Multilingual pre-training has been shown to significantly improve the model's capabilities to perform tasks in any of the supported languages, even without fine-tuning in the application language. For example, if we fine-tune the model to the task of sentiment identification in English and Croatian, it is capable of generalizing its acquired knowledge on sentiment identification to other languages that were included in the pre-training data. Consequently, the resulting fine-tuned model is capable of identifying the correct sentiment in German texts as well, as it has "learned" German words and their connection to the semantically related words in other languages during the multilingual pre-training phase. With the XLM-R-parla model, we go one step further - by additionally pre-training the multilingual XLM-RoBERTa model on the parliamentary domain, we expose it to the domain-specific language. This enhances its performance on tasks involving parliamentary texts, including sentiment identification (Mochtak, Rupnik, and Ljubešić 2024).

We explored this hypothesis during the training process of the ParlaSent model by examining the average difference between the human annotations (on a 6-step scale from 0 to 5) and the output of the models (a real number between 0 and 5), which is also known as Mean Absolute Error or MAE and theoretically ranges from 0 to infinity, with lower values indicating better performance (i.e. smaller error rate). Since MAE is

¹ The model is available at <https://huggingface.co/classla/xlm-r-parla>.

case-dependent, its interpretation must be contextualized based on the specific requirements of the task or dataset. The acceptable error rate for a given case is determined by the level of precision needed for that particular application. For instance, in some contexts, even a small error might be deemed significant and not acceptable, while in others, a larger error could still be within the bounds of acceptability if it doesn't substantially affect the outcomes.

The experiments show that when the model is trained on all annotated languages and then validated on English data only, the mean absolute error (MAE) is 0.675, so well below one single point on the overall 0-5 scale. When we retrain the model, but now using only non-English training data and validate it again on English data only, the model performs similarly well with MAE = 0.756. In a different experiment, when we train a model on all annotated languages and validate it on data from the parliaments of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, and Serbia (BCS data), the MAE is 0.705. When we train a model on all data except the BCS data and validate it on BCS data only, the model still performs very well, with MAE = 0.727. Given the scale of the values to be predicted (0-5), all the reported errors can be considered very close and low overall giving us the confidence the final model will perform well across different languages, and what is more important, also language families (as demonstrated between Slavic languages and English). For further details, a full overview of the training process, and the validation experiments, see Mochtak et al. (2024).

Finally, to provide a robustness check demonstrating that the model performs better than traditional dictionary-based methods and is a valid competitor to GPT models, we run a series of evaluation tests to assess the performance of sentiment annotation using multilingual sentiment dictionaries (Proksch et al. 2019; Rauh 2018), GPT-4o zero-shot classification (OpenAI 2024), and the ParlaSent model. Evaluation was conducted on human-annotated data from the European Parliament and German Bundestag (Proksch et al. 2019; Rauh 2018). This can be considered an external validation test, as the human-annotated datasets are unrelated to the ParlaSent model and were created to validate sentiment scores by different scholars. Annotations produced by the ParlaSent model consistently show significantly better order-based agreement with human-annotated data than the dictionary approach and are comparable with the GPT-4o model, which is computationally expensive and much slower. The results confirm that the ParlaSent model is robust, fast,

and cost-effective. A summary of these tests, along with further details on the data used, is presented in the Appendix.

Using the ParlaSent model

The main motivation behind the paper is to introduce the *ParlaSent model* to the political science community and facilitate its easy application in downstream research tasks. The final model is made available via the HuggingFace Hub and can be downloaded and used free of charge². The model can be applied to most of the available languages with the primary focus on the European language families (i.e., the XLM-R-parla model natural domain). Although trained on the political discourse of European parliaments, the sentence-level data scope allows applications outside its original domain as long as it concerns political discourse (e.g., other speeches, tweets, and political discourse in general). A proper validation is, however, always advisable. As this is a deep learning model based on the transformer architecture, a dedicated graphical card is desirable for the fast processing of input data. As most of the consumer-based laptops do not have one, we have decided to showcase the model's capabilities in an interactive session hosted by Google Colab, providing a free tier for learning and research purposes. The only requirement is a valid Google account. To make it as easy as possible for researchers to start using the model right away, the paper is accompanied by a walkthrough Jupyter Notebook with a step-by-step tutorial for how to apply the model to custom data. To use the notebook, download the .ipynb file from the accompanying repository, upload it to your Google Drive, and double-click it to automatically open it in Google Colab. There, the notebook contains all the important information in a simple step-by-step manner that users can follow. When it comes to the overall structure, the model is deployed as a part of an analytical pipeline that can be divided into two steps: 1) sentence extraction and 2) sentence annotation.

The first step (sentence extraction) requires the processing of raw input text (e.g., a speech) and turning it into individual sentences. Although different options are available, in this tutorial, we use *trankit* (Nguyen et al. 2021), a lightweight transformer-based Python toolkit for multilingual natural language processing in order to parse the input text into sentence-level data. Put simply, users pick the language of a text/corpus

² The model with minimal usage example is available at <https://huggingface.co/classla/xlm-r-parlasent>.

they want to analyze (trankit currently supports 56 languages) and let the convenient local API handle the rest (with no additional costs). After a text is pre-processed (i.e., the body of a text is divided into sentences), the sentence-level data can be fed into the ParlaSent model for sentiment annotation (second part). The whole process is equally straightforward - the model evaluates sentences and returns their estimated sentiment scores on a scale from 0 (fully negative) to 5 (fully positive). Jupyter Notebook presents the whole pipeline in a simple step-by-step tutorial using a mock dataset with 124 speeches.

Real world applications

The model's real potential can be demonstrated only when used with real-world data. We, therefore, support our presentation with two short case studies focused on sentiment in European parliaments between 2015 and 2023. It covers a very dynamic period preceding the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., the migration crisis, economic stagnation, Brexit), the pandemic itself, and the start of the war in Ukraine, providing a complex landscape for sentiment change through time. To make the overview empirically robust, we analyze the sentiment scores across 26 national parliaments covered by the ParlaMint project, an international initiative focused on comparable corpora of parliamentary proceedings in Europe (Erjavec, Kopp, et al. 2023). By using the parliamentary data, it is important to acknowledge that while proceedings provide a formal written record, they may not fully capture the sentiment expressed in spoken debate. Spoken interventions, particularly in unscripted exchanges, often contain emotional nuance, interruptions, and informal language that may be lost or altered in transcription. Additionally, official records may omit or modify strong language deemed inappropriate (Green, Franquiz, and Dixon 1997; Bayley 2004). However, the official transcripts remain an authoritative source of sentiment information, as even heavily redacted text reflect underlying sentiment through contextual cues, structured responses, and rhetorical choices (Li, Bell, and Lai 2022; B. Liu 2020; Wu et al. 2021). Given that sentiment prediction from speech is of much lower quality at this point in time than that from text, we have to conclude that currently the safest approach to large-scale sentiment identification is through textual transcripts of speeches, rather than through speeches themselves (Cai et al. 2025; Avro, Taher, and Mamun 2025).

Following the presented processing pipeline, we first annotate the whole dataset, counting over eight million speeches, using the ParlaSent model. The sentences are ensured to retain their document IDs for easy mapping of the speech-level metadata. We use the extracted sentiment scores in two case studies we treat as show cases but also as validation tests. The first case study demonstrates the application of the model over a purely descriptive task and is organized around two examples: 1) an overview of sentiment scores across time summarizing sentiment trends in European parliaments and 2) an analysis focused on existing differences in coalition/opposition sentiment scores focused on mechanism when MPs switch their position from opposition to coalition. The goals of both examples are not to present particularly new or surprising findings, but rather to demonstrate and empirically validate the utility of the ParlaSent model for mapping sentiment in political discourse with a generally predictable outcome. The second case study focuses on a traditional hypothesis-testing design and explores the hypothesis that European parliaments have gotten more negative in recent years. Again, the goal is to practically demonstrate the usage of produced sentiment scores using a design that is very common in political science research. As a validation test, it focuses on an empirical hypothesis that is generally expected to be true and consistent across different contexts.

Case study 1: Sentiment in European Parliaments

The first example in the first case study utilizes a summary of sentiment scores at the level of entire parliaments through time. Figure 1 visualizes the daily trend across 26 countries as well as the overall trend across Europe. For the visualization, the six-point scale is translated into three categorical variables: negative [0-1] – neutral [2-3] – positive [4-5]. We map the percentage share of these categories in daily discourse as a high-level signal of the prevailing patterns in the studied parliaments. In this context, the data point is the ratio of a specific sentiment on a calendar day.

Figure 1. Overview of sentiment in European parliaments.

Figure 1. Overview of sentiment in European parliaments (continuation).

Note: For each parliament and each day, the percentages of positive, negative, and neutral sentiments were calculated. Given the high variability of the resulting time series, a rolling mean with a one-year window was applied to facilitate long-term sentiment analysis. To highlight the underlying fluctuations in the daily data, we also computed a rolling standard deviation using the same window and plotted it with low opacity behind the rolling mean lines.

Probably the most interesting finding is that positive sentiment is the least prevalent of the three sentiments. Neutral and negative sentiments are always more dominant and often mutually complementary (i.e., mirroring each other's trend). There is no overdominant pattern present across all studied parliaments. The prominence of the mapped sentiment depends on the political and cultural preconditions in each country. To

demonstrate this practically, the biggest observed drop in the ratio of daily negative sentiment occurs in Serbia after the 2020 parliamentary election. The Serbian opposition boycotted the election, criticizing President Aleksandar Vučić and the Serbian Progressive Party (SNS) for authoritarian practices and election manipulation. With no opposition parties running in the election, the Serbian Progressive Party and its allies absolutely dominated the National Assembly, which naturally decreased the contentious nature of debates and the overall level of criticism (i.e., negativity). When the Serbian opposition decided to participate in the 2022 early election again, the ratio of daily negative sentiment increased slightly (as a sign of the return of contentious politics) but still reflected the dominance of SNS and the overall nature of politics in Serbia characterized as a form of competitive authoritarianism (Ilić and Pudar Draško 2022; Bieber 2018).

On the other side of the spectrum, one of the biggest absolute increases in the ratio of negative sentiment can be seen in Spain. Although many countries have experienced increased polarization, resulting in more contentious politics during the pandemic, Spain was severely affected by its additional internal turmoils, leading to extreme polarization and the escalation of political conflicts (e.g., the situation in Catalonia, economic stagnation, the migration crisis, or corruption scandals of the royal family). This created a politically charged environment where negative sentiments were frequently expressed in parliamentary debates and public statements, contributing to the observed trend in the graph (Torcal and Comellas 2022).

The second example we explore is the difference in average sentiment embodied in speeches by MPs when changing their position from being in the opposition on the one hand to becoming part of the ruling coalition on the other. The *turn table* logic goes beyond a simple opposition vs coalition comparison. We explore the sentiment of the same MPs as the function of their position in the parliament. The reported difference may be placed on a scale from -5 (becoming a member of the ruling coalition results in more negative sentiment) to +5 (becoming a member of the ruling coalition results in more positive sentiment). The data at hand fully support the expected change in sentiment for MPs undergoing the transition - MPs representing the ruling parties are overly more positive than when they serve in the opposition (Dijk 2008; Benoit and Laver 2009). The only real exception is Bosnia and Herzegovina, where the reported trend copies the political practice of forming power-sharing governments with very little difference in the sentiment of MPs supporting or

opposing the government. Figure 2 visualizes the differences in average sentiment scores across parliaments with known track of government/opposition changes among mapped MPs. For countries without a shift of power in the studied period (e.g., the UK, Poland, or Hungary), no differences are reported. The differences we map represent the gap between the groups' discourse, potentially signaling the severity of the underlying political conflict (McCoy, Rahman, and Somer 2018; Rheault et al. 2016).

Figure 2. Summary of changes in MPs' sentiment when their position shifts from opposition to becoming part of the ruling coalition that supports the government.

The biggest gap in reported sentiments exists in Turkey ($\text{diff}_{\text{mean}} = 0.87$), Austria ($\text{diff}_{\text{mean}} = 0.83$), and Greece ($\text{diff}_{\text{mean}} = 0.65$). Turkey is a prime example of a country with authoritarian leadership backed by a political party dominating the party system (Justice and Development Party; AKP). Opposition is often oppressed and in direct conflict with the ruling elites. Any co-opting mechanism, where MPs representing the opposition or coalition switch sides, has a profound effect on the overall sentiment. Although this doesn't happen often, when it does, the effect is staggering. A different mechanism potentially plays a role in Austria and Greece. In Austria, the polarized political landscape is strongly affected by the role of the Freedom Party of Austria

(FPÖ). The same goes for Syriza in Greece. Both, when in opposition, are characteristic of anti-establishment and radical rhetoric. When the table turns, the rhetoric changes too, which, apart from the expected effect of just being part of the government, signals also softening of the (radical) rhetoric.

Case study 2: Drivers of negativity

Numerous crises in recent years, ranging from economic and financial shocks to illegal migration, the COVID-19 pandemic, and the war in Ukraine, have altered the emotional landscape in Europe and globally for many. These events have affected our perception of reality and how we feel about the present and the future, most often in negative terms (Rossouw and Greyling 2022; Limone, Toto, and Messina 2022; Barchielli et al. 2022). The same likely applies to political elites—or at least, this is something we expect. Although this argument aligns with common understanding of how politics embodies popular preferences in democratic systems and how negative framing functions in political mobilization (Widmann 2021), a robust empirical test for the hypothesis is still lacking. Therefore, the following case study focuses on exploring the hypothesis that (H1) *European parliaments are becoming increasingly negative over time*, reflecting upon similar trends observed in panel studies (Gruchoła and Sławek-Czochra 2021; Henökl and Jakobsen 2022) and the state of European democracies in general (Nord et al. 2024).

We test the hypothesis with a set of multi-level models focused on presenting an empirical overview of a specific trend in 26 European parliaments between 2015 and 2023 (80% of speeches in ParlaMint database come from this period). We use the ParlaSent model to annotate speeches for their sentiment loading, where the aggregated speech level sentiment score (0-5) is our dependent variable. We fit three models, each controlling for more variables to make the final model more stringent. We control for gender and year of birth as individual-level covariates and left/right ideology, populist status, and coalition/opposition role as party-level covariates. All control variables come from an established body of literature showing that gender (Haselmayer, Dingler, and Jenny 2022), age (McKinney and Rill 2009), ideology (Havey 2020), populist status (Masch and Gabriel 2020), and coalition/opposition division (Louwerse et al. 2021) should execute an effect on sentiment polarity in political discourse. Individual level covariates and the coalition/opposition role come from the ParlaMint dataset, while populist status and left-right ideological position are populated

from the V-Party database (v2pariglef; v2xpa_popul) (Lindberg et al. 2022). For the mixed-model design, we utilize a four-level structure in which speeches are nested in speakers, speakers in political parties, political parties in terms, and terms in countries. This structure should be sufficient to capture the natural hierarchy in the data at hand. Finally, we focus only on the discourse of regular MPs and exclude speeches of moderators, executives, and guests as those might introduce structural biases.

Descriptives are presented in Table 1. Table 2 summarizes the results of the three models. The analysis shows that time, our main independent variable, has a negative and statistically significant effect across all three models. Focusing on Model 3 as our final model, we can see that every year contributes to the decrease of the average level of sentiment by 0.01. In other words, eight years of parliamentary data have seen a decrease of the averaged sentiment by 0.08. As the $SD=1.15$, this is a small effect but, at the same time, in a relatively short period of time. Figure 3 visualizes the marginal effect of time on the sentiment score in a more intuitive way. This confirms our hypothesis and shows that parliaments align with the general trends in Europe, but the drop is not as big as one would expect considering the decade of crisis Europe has experienced (migration crisis, COVID-19 pandemic, and War in Ukraine) (Henökl and Jakobsen 2022; Nord et al. 2024).

The rest of the control variables behave as expected. Male MPs are more negative than female MPs (e.g., hypothesis about genderized sentiment) (Peterson and Zurbriggen 2010), younger MPs are more negative than older representatives (hypothesis about discontent youth) (Debus and Himmelrath 2022), populist parties are more negative than non-populist parties (e.g., hypothesis about good people versus bad elites) (Gerstlé and Nai 2019), and opposition political parties are more negative than coalition parties (e.g., hypothesis about the role of opposition in the democratic system) (Benoit and Laver 2009). Ideology does not show any statistically significant effect in the model. The results demonstrate how the classification model can be used to answer substantive questions within a traditional hypothesis-testing design. In this context, the classifier produces sentiment scores, which are used as quantified features at the level of speeches and then serve as a variable in a regression model.

Table 1: Summary of descriptives

Variable	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
Sentiment	2.12	1.17	-0.23	5.80
Time (years)	2018.23	2.13	2015.00	2023.00
Gender (F)	0.28	0.45	0.00	1.00
Year of birth	1969.64	9.91	1923.00	2001.00
Ideology	0.10	1.60	-3.94	4.17
Populist status	0.42	0.30	0.03	0.98
Opposition status	0.46	0.50	0.00	1.00

Table 2: Summary of models

	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	B	S.E.	Sig.	B	S.E.	Sig.	B	S.E.	Sig.
(Intercept)	44.38	1.22	***	35.62	1.51	***	30.34	1.79	***
Time (years)	-0.02	0.00	***	-0.02	0.00	***	-0.01	0.00	***
Gender (male)				-0.1	0.01	***	-0.08	0.01	***
Year of birth				0.001	0.00	**	0.00	0.00	*
Ideology (L-R)							-0.01	0.01	
Populist status							-0.3	0.06	***
Opposition status							-0.34	0.01	***

n: 3 578 955 / *MPs*: 23 283 / *n*: 2 619 963 / *MPs*: 14 858 / *n*: 1 900 605 / *MPs*: 11 206 /
parties: 800 / *terms*: 90 / *parties*: 658 / *terms*: 74 / *parties*: 358 / *terms*: 72 /
parliaments: 26 *parliaments*: 22 *parliaments*: 22

Note: (p-value): † < 0.1; * < 0.05; ** < 0.01; *** < 0.001. We deliberately did not use the same dataset in all three models to demonstrate how additional covariates reduce the size of available data. The results are substantively the same when the dataset used in Model 3 is used also in Model 1 and Model 2.

Figure 3: Visualization of marginal effect of the variable *Time* in Model 3.

Conclusion

In politics, when reason and emotions collide, emotion invariably wins (Westen 2008). Recent years have highlighted the fragility of European societies when faced with crises accompanied by fear and anxiety. These mechanisms are not new; they have been integral to politics for centuries, even millennia. However, what sets recent developments apart is the unprecedented access to and reach of these processes. Studying them is crucial to better understanding the dynamics of politics and its evolution. This paper aims to contribute to this field by presenting a robust classification model specifically designed for the political domain of European democracies, with a scope that extends beyond the English-speaking world.

The contribution of this paper is at least threefold. First, it introduces a transformer model trained for sentiment classification to the political science community. The model is robust enough to be applied to most European languages without further fine-tuning or modifications. It was shown to perform significantly better than the traditional dictionary-based approaches, and comparably to the slower and more expensive large language models available through APIs. One of the main benefits of the ParlaSent model is that it significantly lowers the barrier to using the domain-specific sentiment classifier for both high- and low-resource European languages. The model is freely available on Hugging Face Hub and can be used at no cost by anyone. We provide a Jupyter notebook with a working pipeline for processing raw text in the cloud using the free tier of Google Colab. The model can also be downloaded and run locally. We guide users through the entire process step by step, with comments and instructions, so that anyone can upload a simple spreadsheet and start analyzing political texts within minutes.

Second, the paper presents practical examples of how to use the model in downstream research tasks with the focus on a less technical and more practical outlook relevant for a wide range of political science research problems. We deem the model to be useful for both qualitative and quantitative scholars seeking to answer different research questions. The common path includes annotation of raw textual data with the ParlaSent model and then using the outcome to study the phenomena one is interested in. For qualitative scholars, this may include flagging and extracting text snippets around specific keywords that can be analyzed

qualitatively as a part of a broader discourse analysis (e.g., analysis of frames). Quantitative scholars can use sentiment scores in traditional hypothesis testing and extract sentiment as a feature of text (e.g., speeches, tweets, or documents). Both approaches benefit from a straightforward sentiment classifier capable of annotating thousands of documents quickly and cost-effectively. While speed is highly dependent on the available hardware, it is possible to process thousands of sentences and hundreds of documents per minute.

Finally, the model is part of a bigger effort to facilitate the usage of large language models in political science, especially for languages that are low-resourced and for users that have no technical background. The sentiment classifier was trained on top of the XLM-R-parla model, which is the XLM-RoBERTa multilingual transformer model adapted to the political domain by being additionally pre-trained on 1.72 billion words of parliamentary debates from the ParlaMint and the EuroParl datasets (Mochtak, Rupnik, and Ljubešić 2024). Although this model was fine-tuned to perform a sentiment classification task, other tasks in the political domain, such as text classification, regression, or span identification, are possible with minimal additional fine-tuning. This flexibility makes the model a valuable tool for political scientists who seek to analyze large-scale textual data across various languages.

Building on this foundation, we aim to further explore the potential of multilingual transformer technology to address challenges in political science, particularly with the ParlaMint corpus. Our development of transformer models for the Comparative Agenda Project topic classification serves as a stepping stone, leveraging LLM-annotated data and fine-tuning a model with fewer than 1 billion parameters. This approach improves efficiency and extends NLP tools into political research areas where human annotations are limited or costly. We envision using NLP to analyze political discourse, detect shifts in public opinion, and examine the influence of legislative speeches on policy outcomes, contributing to political analysis and decision-making.

References

Abercrombie, Gavin, and Riza Batista-Navarro. 2018. “‘Aye’ or ‘No’? Speech-Level Sentiment Analysis of Hansard UK Parliamentary Debate Transcripts.” In *Proceedings of the Eleventh International*

- Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2018)*. Miyazaki, Japan: European Language Resources Association (ELRA). <https://aclanthology.org/L18-1659>.
- . 2020. “Sentiment and Position-Taking Analysis of Parliamentary Debates: A Systematic Literature Review.” *Journal of Computational Social Science* 3 (1): 245–70. doi:10.1007/s42001-019-00060-w.
- Abramowitz, Alan I., and Steven Webster. 2016. “The Rise of Negative Partisanship and the Nationalization of U.S. Elections in the 21st Century.” *Electoral Studies* 41 (March): 12–22. doi:10.1016/j.electstud.2015.11.001.
- Avro, Shamin Bin Habib, Taieba Taher, and Nursadul Mamun. 2025. “EmoTech: A Multi-Modal Speech Emotion Recognition Using Multi-Source Low-Level Information with Hybrid Recurrent Network.” arXiv. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2501.12674.
- Bansal, Mohit, Claire Cardie, and Lillian Lee. 2008. “The Power of Negative Thinking: Exploiting Label Disagreement in the Min-Cut Classification Framework.” In *Coling 2008: Companion Volume: Posters*, 15–18. Manchester, UK: Coling 2008 Organizing Committee. <https://aclanthology.org/C08-2004>.
- Barchielli, Benedetta, Clarissa Cricenti, Francesca Gallè, Elita Anna Sabella, Fabrizio Liguori, Giovanna Da Molin, Giorgio Liguori, et al. 2022. “Climate Changes, Natural Resources Depletion, COVID-19 Pandemic, and Russian-Ukrainian War: What Is the Impact on Habits Change and Mental Health?” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19 (19). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute: 11929. doi:10.3390/ijerph191911929.
- Bayley, Paul. 2004. *Cross-Cultural Perspectives on Parliamentary Discourse*. Discourse Approaches to Politics, Society and Culture. Amsterdam: Benjamins.
- Benoit, Kenneth, and Michael Laver. 2009. *Party Policy in Modern Democracies*. Transferred to digital print. London: Routledge. <http://catdir.loc.gov/catdir/enhancements/fy0654/2006014032-d.html>.
- Bieber, Florian. 2018. “Patterns of Competitive Authoritarianism in the Western Balkans.” *East European Politics* 34 (3). Routledge: 337–54. doi:10.1080/21599165.2018.1490272.
- Cai, Yujian, Xingguang Li, Yingyu Zhang, Jinsong Li, Fazheng Zhu, and Lin Rao. 2025. “Multimodal Sentiment Analysis Based on Multi-Layer Feature Fusion and Multi-Task Learning.” *Scientific Reports* 15 (1). Nature Publishing Group: 2126. doi:10.1038/s41598-025-85859-6.
- Chilton, Paul A. 2004. *Analysing Political Discourse: Theory and Practice*. London: Routledge.
- Das, Ringki, and Thoudam Doren Singh. 2023. “Multimodal Sentiment Analysis: A Survey of Methods, Trends, and Challenges.” *ACM Computing Surveys* 55 (13s): 270:1-270:38. doi:10.1145/3586075.
- Debus, Marc, and Noam Himmelrath. 2022. “Advocates of Climate Action? The Age of Members of Parliament and Their Activity in Legislative Debates on Climate Change.” *Climate Action* 1 (1). Nature Publishing Group: 1–13. doi:10.1007/s44168-022-00017-2.
- Dijk, Teun A. van. 2008. *Discourse and Power*. Basingstoke: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Druckman, James N., Samara Klar, Yanna Krupnikov, Matthew Levendusky, and John Barry Ryan. 2021. “Affective Polarization, Local Contexts and Public Opinion in America.” *Nature Human Behaviour* 5 (1). Nature Publishing Group: 28–38. doi:10.1038/s41562-020-01012-5.
- Duval, Dominic, and François Pétry. 2016. “L’analyse Automatisée Du Ton Médiatique : Construction et Utilisation de La Version Française Du Lexicoder Sentiment Dictionary.” *Canadian Journal of Political Science/Revue Canadienne de Science Politique* 49 (2): 197–220. doi:10.1017/S000842391600055X.
- Erjavec, Tomaž, Matyáš Kopp, Maciej Ogrodniczuk, Petya Osenova, Manex Agirrezabal, Tommaso Agnoloni, José Aires, et al. 2023. “Multilingual comparable corpora of parliamentary debates ParlaMint 4.0.” <https://www.clarin.eu/content/parlamint>, October. CLARIN ERIC. <https://www.clarin.si/repository/xmlui/handle/11356/1859>.
- Erjavec, Tomaž, Maciej Ogrodniczuk, Petya Osenova, Nikola Ljubešić, Kiril Simov, Andrej Pančur, Michal Rudolf, et al. 2023. “The ParlaMint Corpora of Parliamentary Proceedings.” *Language Resources and Evaluation* 57 (1): 415–48. doi:10.1007/s10579-021-09574-0.
- Finkel, Eli J., Christopher A. Bail, Mina Cikara, Peter H. Ditto, Shanto Iyengar, Samara Klar, Lilliana Mason, et al. 2020. “Political Sectarianism in America.” *Science* 370 (6516). American Association for the Advancement of Science: 533–36. doi:10.1126/science.abe1715.
- Garrett, R. Kelly, Shira Dvir Gvirsman, Benjamin K. Johnson, Yariv Tsfati, Rachel Neo, and Aysenur Dal. 2014. “Implications of Pro- and Counterattitudinal Information Exposure for Affective Polarization.”

- Human Communication Research* 40 (3). United Kingdom: Wiley-Blackwell Publishing Ltd.: 309–32. doi:10.1111/hcre.12028.
- Gerstlé, Jacques, and Alessandro Nai. 2019. “Negativity, Emotionality and Populist Rhetoric in Election Campaigns Worldwide, and Their Effects on Media Attention and Electoral Success.” *European Journal of Communication* 34 (4). SAGE Publications Ltd: 410–44. doi:10.1177/0267323119861875.
- González-Bailón, Sandra, and Georgios Paltoglou. 2015. “Signals of Public Opinion in Online Communication: A Comparison of Methods and Data Sources.” *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 659 (1). SAGE Publications Inc: 95–107. doi:10.1177/0002716215569192.
- Green, Judith, Maria Franquiz, and Carol Dixon. 1997. “The Myth of the Objective Transcript: Transcribing as a Situated Act.” *TESOL Quarterly* 31 (1). [Wiley, Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages, Inc. (TESOL)]: 172–76. doi:10.2307/3587984.
- Gruchola, Małgorzata, and Małgorzata Sławek-Czochra. 2021. “‘The Culture of Fear’ of Inhabitants of EU Countries in Their Reaction to the COVID-19 Pandemic – A Study Based on the Reports of the Eurobarometer.” *Safety Science* 135 (March): 105140. doi:10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105140.
- Haselmayer, Martin, Sarah C Dingler, and Marcelo Jenny. 2022. “How Women Shape Negativity in Parliamentary Speeches—A Sentiment Analysis of Debates in the Austrian Parliament.” *Parliamentary Affairs* 75 (4): 867–86. doi:10.1093/pa/gsab045.
- Havey, Nicholas Francis. 2020. “Partisan Public Health: How Does Political Ideology Influence Support for COVID-19 Related Misinformation?” *Journal of Computational Social Science* 3 (2): 319–42. doi:10.1007/s42001-020-00089-2.
- Henökl, Thomas, and Tor Georg Jakobsen. 2022. “The Rising Fear of Terrorism and the Emergence of a European Security Governance Space: Citizen Perceptions and EU Counterterrorism Cooperation.” *Journal of Contemporary European Studies* 30 (3). Routledge: 536–51. doi:10.1080/14782804.2021.1958202.
- Honkela, Timo, Jaakko Korhonen, Krista Lagus, and Esa Saarinen. 2014. “Five-Dimensional Sentiment Analysis of Corpora, Documents and Words.” In *Advances in Self-Organizing Maps and Learning Vector Quantization*, edited by Thomas Villmann, Frank-Michael Schleich, Marika Kaden, and Mandy Lange, 209–18. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing. Cham: Springer International Publishing. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-07695-9_20.
- Ilić, Vujo, and Gazela Pudar Draško. 2022. “2022 Elections in Serbia: The Return of the Opposition?” *Contemporary Southeastern Europe* 9 (2). Universität Graz: 1–14.
- Iyengar, Shanto, Gaurav Sood, and Yphtach Lelkes. 2012. “Affect, Not Ideology: A Social Identity Perspective on Polarization.” *Public Opinion Quarterly* 76 (3): 405–31. doi:10.1093/poq/nfs038.
- Koehn, Philipp. 2005. “Europarl: A Parallel Corpus for Statistical Machine Translation.” In *Proceedings of Machine Translation Summit X: Papers*, 79–86. Phuket, Thailand. <https://aclanthology.org/2005.mtsummit-papers.11>.
- Kroon, Anne, Kasper Welbers, Damian Trilling, and Wouter van Atteveldt. 2023. “Advancing Automated Content Analysis for a New Era of Media Effects Research: The Key Role of Transfer Learning.” *Communication Methods and Measures* 0 (0). Routledge: 1–21. doi:10.1080/19312458.2023.2261372.
- Lakoff, George. 2004. *Don't Think of an Elephant*. White River Junction: Chelsea Green.
- Laurer, Moritz, Wouter van Atteveldt, Andreu Casas, and Kasper Welbers. 2024. “Less Annotating, More Classifying: Addressing the Data Scarcity Issue of Supervised Machine Learning with Deep Transfer Learning and BERT-NLI.” *Political Analysis* 32 (1): 84–100. doi:10.1017/pan.2023.20.
- Li, Yuanchao, Peter Bell, and Catherine Lai. 2022. “Fusing ASR Outputs in Joint Training for Speech Emotion Recognition.” arXiv. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2110.15684.
- Limone, Pierpaolo, Giusi Antonia Toto, and Giovanni Messina. 2022. “Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine War on Stress and Anxiety in Students: A Systematic Review.” *Frontiers in Psychiatry* 13 (November). Frontiers. doi:10.3389/fpsy.2022.1081013.
- Lindberg, Staffan I., Nils Düpont, Masaaki Higashijima, Yaman Berker Kavasoglu, Kyle L. Marquardt, Michael Bernhard, Holger Döring, et al. 2022. “Varieties of Party Identity and Organization (V-Party).” <https://doi.org/10.23696/vpartydsv2>.

- Liu, Bing. 2020. *Sentiment Analysis: Mining Opinions, Sentiments, and Emotions*. Second edition. Studies in Natural Language Processing. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108639286>.
- Liu, Yinhan, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. 2019. "RoBERTa: A Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach." arXiv. doi:10.48550/arXiv.1907.11692.
- Louwerson, Tom, Ulrich Sieberer, Or Tuttnauer, and Rudy B. Andeweg. 2021. "Opposition in Times of Crisis: COVID-19 in Parliamentary Debates." *West European Politics* 44 (5–6). Routledge: 1025–51. doi:10.1080/01402382.2021.1886519.
- Masch, Lena, and Oscar W. Gabriel. 2020. "How Emotional Displays of Political Leaders Shape Citizen Attitudes: The Case of German Chancellor Angela Merkel." *German Politics* 29 (2). Routledge: 158–79. doi:10.1080/09644008.2019.1657096.
- Mason, Lilliana. 2015. "'I Disrespectfully Agree': The Differential Effects of Partisan Sorting on Social and Issue Polarization." *American Journal of Political Science* 59 (1): 128–45. doi:10.1111/ajps.12089.
- . 2018. *Uncivil Agreement: How Politics Became Our Identity*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/U/bo27527354.html>.
- McCoy, Jennifer, Tahmina Rahman, and Murat Somer. 2018. "Polarization and the Global Crisis of Democracy: Common Patterns, Dynamics, and Pernicious Consequences for Democratic Polities." *American Behavioral Scientist* 62 (1). SAGE Publications Inc: 16–42. doi:10.1177/0002764218759576.
- McKinney, Mitchell S., and Leslie A. Rill. 2009. "Not Your Parents' Presidential Debates: Examining the Effects of the CNN/YouTube Debates on Young Citizens' Civic Engagement." *Communication Studies* 60 (4). Routledge: 392–406. doi:10.1080/10510970903110001.
- Merritt, Rick. 2022. "What Is a Transformer Model?" *NVIDIA Blog*. March 25. <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/2022/03/25/what-is-a-transformer-model/>.
- Mochtak, Michal, Peter Rupnik, and Nikola Ljubešić. 2024. "The ParlaSent Multilingual Training Dataset for Sentiment Identification in Parliamentary Proceedings." In *Proceedings of the 2024 Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-COLING 2024)*, edited by Nicoletta Calzolari, Min-Yen Kan, Veronique Hoste, Alessandro Lenci, Sakriani Sakti, and Nianwen Xue, 16024–36. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lrec-main.1393>.
- Nguyen, Minh Van, Viet Dac Lai, Amir Pouran Ben Veyseh, and Thien Huu Nguyen. 2021. "Trankit: A Light-Weight Transformer-Based Toolkit for Multilingual Natural Language Processing." In *Proceedings of the 16th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, 80–90. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi:10.18653/v1/2021.eacl-demos.10.
- Nord, Marina, Martin Lundstedt, David Altman, Fabio Angiolillo, Cecilia Borella, Tiago Fernandes, Lisa Gastaldi, Ana Good God, Natalia Natsika, and Staffan I. Lindberg. 2024. "Democracy Report 2024: Democracy Winning and Losing at the Ballot." University of Gothenburg: V-Dem Institute. https://v-dem.net/documents/43/v-dem_dr2024_lowres.pdf.
- OpenAI. 2024. "Hello GPT-4o." May 13. <https://openai.com/index/hello-gpt-4o>.
- Peterson, Bill E., and Eileen L. Zurbriggen. 2010. "Gender, Sexuality, and the Authoritarian Personality." *Journal of Personality* 78 (6): 1801–26. doi:10.1111/j.1467-6494.2010.00670.x.
- Piazza, James A. 2020. "Politician Hate Speech and Domestic Terrorism." *International Interactions* 46 (3). Routledge: 431–53.
- Powell, Bingham G. 2004. "Political Representation in Comparative Politics." *Annual Review of Political Science* 7. Annual Reviews: 273–96. doi:10.1146/ANNUREV.POLISCI.7.012003.104815.
- Proksch, Sven-Oliver, Will Lowe, Jens Wäckerle, and Stuart Soroka. 2019. "Multilingual Sentiment Analysis: A New Approach to Measuring Conflict in Legislative Speeches." *Legislative Studies Quarterly* 44 (1): 97–131. doi:10.1111/lsq.12218.
- Proksch, Sven-Oliver, and Jonathan B. Slapin. 2015. *The Politics of Parliamentary Debate: Parties, Rebels and Representation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Rauh, Christian. 2018. "Validating a Sentiment Dictionary for German Political Language—a Workbench Note." *Journal of Information Technology & Politics* 15 (4). Routledge: 319–43. doi:10.1080/19331681.2018.1485608.

- Rheault, Ludovic, Kaspar Beelen, Christopher Cochrane, and Graeme Hirst. 2016. "Measuring Emotion in Parliamentary Debates with Automated Textual Analysis." *PLOS ONE* 11 (12). Public Library of Science: e0168843. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0168843.
- Rossouw, Stephanié, and Talita Greyling. 2022. "Collective Emotions and Macro-Level Shocks: COVID-19 vs the Ukrainian War." Working Paper 1210. GLO Discussion Paper. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/267148>.
- Tan, Kian Long, Chin Poo Lee, and Kian Ming Lim. 2023. "A Survey of Sentiment Analysis: Approaches, Datasets, and Future Research." *Applied Sciences* 13 (7). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute: 4550. doi:10.3390/app13074550.
- Torcál, Mariano, and Josep M. Comellas. 2022. "Affective Polarisation in Times of Political Instability and Conflict. Spain from a Comparative Perspective." *South European Society and Politics* 27 (1). Routledge: 1–26. doi:10.1080/13608746.2022.2044236.
- Vaswani, Ashish, Google Brain, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N Gomez, \Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. 2017. "Attention Is All You Need." In *NIPS'17: Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, 6000–6010. doi:10.5555/3295222.3295349.
- Westen, Drew. 2008. *The Political Brain: The Role of Emotion in Deciding the Fate of the Nation*. New York: PublicAffairs.
- Widmann, Tobias. 2021. "How Emotional Are Populists Really? Factors Explaining Emotional Appeals in the Communication of Political Parties." *Political Psychology* 42 (1): 163–81. doi:10.1111/pops.12693.
- Widmann, Tobias, and Maximilian Wich. 2023. "Creating and Comparing Dictionary, Word Embedding, and Transformer-Based Models to Measure Discrete Emotions in German Political Text." *Political Analysis* 31 (4): 626–41. doi:10.1017/pan.2022.15.
- Wu, Yang, Zijie Lin, Yanyan Zhao, Bing Qin, and Li-Nan Zhu. 2021. "A Text-Centered Shared-Private Framework via Cross-Modal Prediction for Multimodal Sentiment Analysis." In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL-IJCNLP 2021*, edited by Chengqing Zong, Fei Xia, Wenjie Li, and Roberto Navigli, 4730–38. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi:10.18653/v1/2021.findings-acl.417.
- Young, Lori, and Stuart Soroka. 2012. "Affective News: The Automated Coding of Sentiment in Political Texts." *Political Communication* 29 (2). Taylor & Francis Group: 205–31. doi:10.1080/10584609.2012.671234.